

Моя профессиональная
карьера

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER

ISSN
2782-4365

Проверить
номер:

Научно-образовательный электронный журнал

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ

Выпуск №68-4 (том 2)
(ноябрь, 2025)

Периодичность выпуска: 1 раз в неделю
Сайт: mpcareer.ru/oinv21veke. Почта: obrmpcareer@mail.ru

Международный научно-образовательный
электронный журнал
«ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ»

ISSN 2782-4365

УДК 37

ББК 94

**Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал
«ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ». Выпуск №68-4 (том 2) (ноябрь,
2025). Дата выхода в свет: 01.12.2025.**

Журнал объединяет авторов на территории стран СНГ и помогает обмениваться передовыми научно-образовательными исследованиями.

Содержит научные статьи отечественных и зарубежных авторов по экономическим, техническим, философским, юридическим и другим наукам.

Миссия научно-образовательного электронного журнала «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ» состоит в поддержке интереса читателей к оригинальным исследованиям и инновационным подходам в различных тематических направлениях, которые способствуют распространению лучшей отечественной и зарубежной практики в интернет пространстве.

Целевая аудитория журнала охватывает работников сферы науки и образования (педагоги, учителя, ученые, преподаватели, научные сотрудники, бакалавры, магистранты, аспиранты).

Материалы публикуются в авторской редакции. За соблюдение законов об интеллектуальной собственности и за содержание статей ответственность несут авторы статей. Мнение редакции может не совпадать с мнением авторов статей. При использовании и заимствовании материалов ссылка на издание обязательна.

© ООО «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА»

© Коллектив авторов

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Пестерев С.В. – гл. редактор, отв. за выпуск

Абдурасулов Абдуллажон Абдукаримович	доктор философии педагогических наук
Азамов Жасурбек Муродович	доктор философии в области юриспруденции
Артикова Мухайохон Ботиралиевна	доктор педагогических наук, доцент
Ахмедов Ботиржон Равшанович	доктор философии в филолог. науках (PhD), доцент
Батурин Сергей Петрович	кандидат исторических наук, доцент
Бекжанова Айнура Мархабаевна	доктор философии по педагог. наукам (PhD), доцент
Бекжанова Гулнара Маркабаевна	кандидат медицинских наук, преподаватель
Боброва Людмила Владимировна	кандидат технических наук, доцент
Богданова Татьяна Владимировна	кандидат филологических наук, доцент
Ботиров Аминжон Розимбоевич	кандидат биологических наук, доцент
Демьянова Людмила Михайловна	кандидат медицинских наук, доцент
Еремеева Людмила Эмировна	кандидат технических наук, доцент
Жуманова Фатима Ураловна	кандидат педагогических наук, доцент
Засядько Константин Иванович	доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Исломова Саидахон Тургуновна	доктор философии по техническим наукам (PhD), доцент
Кабулова Мехрибан Толыбаевна	доктор философии по педагог. наукам (PhD)
Казакова Раъно Машрабаевна	доктор философии по филологическим наукам (PhD)
Кодиров Хасанбой Орибжонович	доктор философии педагогических наук
Колесников Олег Михайлович	кандидат физико-математических наук, доцент
Коробейникова Екатерина Викторовна	кандидат экономических наук, доцент
Ланцева Татьяна Георгиевна	кандидат экономических наук, доцент
Мухамедова Лола Джураевна	доктор философии по филологическим наукам (PhD)
Нарзикулова Фируза Ботировна	доктор психологических наук
Нобель Артем Робертович	кандидат юридических наук, доцент
Ноздрина Наталья Александровна	кандидат педагогических наук, доцент
Нуржанов Сабит Узакбаевич	доктор историч. наук (dsc), старший научный сотрудник
Олтаев Шавкат Собирович	кандидат экономических наук, доцент
Павлов Евгений Владимирович	кандидат исторических наук, доцент
Петрова Юлия Валентиновна	кандидат биологических наук, доцент
Попов Сергей Викторович	доктор юридических наук, профессор

Muhammadjonov Davron, Zaynobiddinov Yusufxon IQTISODIY ISLOHOTLAR, XUSUSIY MULKNING SHAKLLANISHI. O'ZBEKISTONDA BOZOR MUNOSABATLARINING RIVOJLANISHI	370
Sunnatova Dinara Mansur qizi ESHITISH QOBILİYATI CHEKLANGAN BOLALARNING NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA VIZUAL YORDAMLAR ROLI	383
Komolova Guljahon Sherzodbek Qizi INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA GENDER MASALASI	387
Karimov Muhammadrahim Salimjon ogli THE ROLE OF MORALITY IN SOCIAL LIFE AND ITS CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES	394
Enejan Agamyradova, Enejan Hidayberdiyeva, Patma Igdyrova POSSIBILITIES OF OBTAINING POTASSIUM NITRATE FROM POTASSIUM CHLORIDE	399
Shomuslimova Malika MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TARIXI	404
Uralov Ilxom Komil o'g'li NASLIY KASALLIKLAR VA TUG'MA NUQSONLARNING OLDINI OLISH YO'LLARI	408
Bulishev Ibrohimjon Ilxomjon ugli THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TPR IN TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS	416
Muhammadjonov Muhammad Yusuf, Mamadaliyev Behruzбек O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA IJTIMOİY O'ZGARISHLAR	421
Мелебаева Говхер Довулбаевна ИНЖЕНЕРНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ АНТЕННО-ФИДЕРНЫХ УСТРОЙСТВ В СПУТНИКОВЫХ СИСТЕМАХ СВЯЗИ НОВОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ	436
Gulnaza Matkarimova, Meredova Guncha, Cinar Nuriyeva TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCING COLOUR CATCHER FABRIC	441
Нафасов Ганишер Абдурашидович, Баходиров Музроб Даниер угли РОЛЬ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ В РАЗВИТИИ ЖИЗНЕННЫХ НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ	446
Nasriddinova Tursunoy Yusupovna QORIN BO'SHLIG'I O'TKIR JAROHATLARIDA ERTA DIAGNOSTIKA VA JARROHLIK TAKTIKASI	453
Ogulkeyik Almazova, Enejan Ishanova, Odilbek Reyimov DEVELOPING WATER-ABSORBING POROUS ASPHALT FOR SUSTAINABLE ROADS	460
Овезекова Айгозель, Мирзоева Дильфуза Ахметджанова PRAGMATIC FUNCTIONS OF DISCOURSE MARKERS IN MODERN SPOKEN ENGLISH	465

UDC: 372.881.111.1.

ORCID:0000-0002-5274-6141

ФИО автора(-ов): *Bulishev Ibrohimjon Ilxomjon ugli*

2nd year master's student of Andijan branch of Turon University.

Название публикации: «THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TPR IN TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY TO YOUNG LEARNERS»

Abstract: This article analyzes the role and effectiveness of the Total Physical Response (TPR) method in teaching English vocabulary to primary school students based on scientific sources. The psychological, didactic and linguistic-methodological foundations of the TPR method are explained, as well as practical exercises and recommendations for mastering vocabulary using this method are given.

Keywords: TPR, lexis, primary education, methodology, movement-based learning, advantage, vocabulary, didactics, method

Аннотация: В статье анализируется роль и эффективность метода полного физического реагирования (TPR) в обучении начальной школы английской лексике на основе научных источников. Разъясняются психологические, дидактические и лингвистико-методические основы метода TPR, а также приводятся практические упражнения и рекомендации по освоению лексики с использованием данного метода.

Ключевые слова: TPR, лексика, начальное образование, методика, обучение на основе движения, преимущество, словарный запас, дидактика, метод

Introduction. In recent years, learning foreign languages has become a necessity not only in our country but also worldwide due to the growing need for intercultural communication. Consequently, numerous methods and techniques for teaching foreign languages have been developed. Over time, various approaches have been applied in language teaching, including traditional methods that focus on the overall structure of the language and emphasize teaching grammar rules [6;23-48]. The most commonly used method is the Grammar-Translation method, where

memorization is prioritized [7]. However, modern language teaching prioritizes communication, emphasizing the practical use of language in real-life situations and encouraging students to improve their speaking skills both inside and outside the classroom. Therefore, several communicative and interactive methods, such as Total Physical Response (TPR), have been employed to create an authentic learning environment in the classroom [5;35-36].

Literature review. Active engagement with the language is essential for effective learning [2;67]. Vocabulary plays a central role in this process. Active vocabulary acquisition can be achieved not only by familiarizing students with new words but also by enabling them to understand and use these words through structured practice and context. A sufficient vocabulary is necessary for meaningful communication, allowing learners to express themselves adequately. Wilkins emphasized the importance of vocabulary, stating: “Without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed” [10;111].

In the context of TPR, vocabulary learning becomes more effective because students physically respond to verbal commands, linking words with actions, which strengthens memory retention and enhances comprehension. Thus, vocabulary acquisition, combined with kinesthetic activities, is one of the core components of language learning and teaching [4;118].

TPR, that is, the Total Physical Response method, has been recognized as an effective approach specifically for primary school learners.

The TPR method, developed by James Asher, ensures natural language acquisition by first receiving the language through listening and then reinforcing it through physical action [1;15]. According to Asher, learners should not be forced to speak; rather, speech should emerge naturally [1;47].

Since school-age children have short attention spans, a preference for play-based activities, and a high need to learn through objects and actions, TPR is considered one of the most suitable methods for this age group [3;102].

In J. Asher’s studies, the central principle of TPR is “comprehension-based input.” That is, the learner first understands, then acts, and finally develops speech

[1;35]. This model aligns with the natural language acquisition process of young children.

Brown studied the effect of the TPR method on retention and demonstrated that vocabulary linked with actions is retained twice as fast [3;89]. He emphasized that physical activity serves as a key catalyst in language acquisition.

Brewster and Ellis describe TPR in primary classes as “the most natural model of kinesthetic learning” [4;118]. According to them, teaching vocabulary through commands, games, stories, and real objects turns students into active participants [4;121].

Cameron emphasizes that the integration of multimodal methods (visual, auditory, action) during vocabulary instruction strengthens learners’ cognitive processes [5;104]. TPR is one of the methods that possesses this multimodal feature.

Pinter discusses the motivational impact of TPR games, noting that exercises such as “Simon Says” keep young learners actively engaged during lessons [8;91].

Larsen-Freeman, while highlighting the advantages of TPR, also points out its limitations: additional methods are required for teaching abstract vocabulary [9;75].

Discussion. The effectiveness of TPR is based on several psychological mechanisms. First, it reduces stress, since learners are not forced to speak, which prevents fear related to language learning [1;55]. Second, both hemispheres of the brain are actively engaged: actions involve the right hemisphere, while language processing involves the left hemisphere [3;102]. Third, information encoded through actions is stored more effectively in long-term memory [3;244]. Fourth, TPR follows a natural language acquisition model: the learner first listens, then acts, understands, and finally begins to speak [5;67].

There are several practical techniques for teaching English vocabulary based on TPR, which help students memorize words more easily. The main element of TPR is commands, such as Stand up, Sit down, Touch the table, Open your book. These exercises are highly effective for teaching verbs and classroom objects [8;91]. Additionally, working with real objects helps learners memorize words faster: pencil,

book, apple. Cameron considers teaching through real objects the most effective visual-kinesthetic model for young learners [5;104].

Storytelling through TPR also develops students' imagination: The cat jumps, the dog runs, the girl smiles, the boy swims, the monkey climbs. Brewster calls this the "integral learning model" [4;118].

Young learners acquire English vocabulary more effectively through games. One of these is "Simon Says." The main purpose of this game is to teach verbs, action words, body parts, and short phrases, while focusing attention, memorization, and linking action with speech. In this game, the teacher gives commands starting with "Simon says..." for example: "Simon says, touch your head" or "Simon says, jump three times." If the command does not start with "Simon says," students do not act. Mistakes result in elimination or other rules being applied.

The connection of this game to TPR lies in combining action and speech, allowing learners to acquire new words naturally. When students perform the action, they remember the word, and visual and kinesthetic memory are actively engaged. The game increases motivation and makes the lesson interactive [4;118].

Other games compatible with TPR include "Action Relay" and "Flashcard Move." These games also help young learners focus their attention and make lessons more engaging [8;109].

Conclusion. In conclusion, the TPR method is one of the most effective approaches for teaching English vocabulary to young learners because it aligns with their natural learning model. Literature review shows that TPR helps learners acquire words quickly, solidly, and motivationally by combining listening, action, and visual components. The method is even more effective when integrated with commands, stories, real objects, and age-appropriate games designed according to learners' interests.

References

1. Asher J. Learning Another Language Through Actions. Los Gatos: Sky Oaks, 1977.

2. Aykaç, N. Yabancı Dil Olarak Türkçe Öğretiminin Genel Tarihçesi Ve Bu Alanda Kullanılan Yöntemler. *Turkish Studies International Periodical For The Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 10(3), 161-173. 2015.
3. Brown H. *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. Pearson, 2014.
4. Brewster J., Ellis G. *The Primary English Teacher's Guide*. Longman, 2010.
5. Cameron L. *Teaching Languages to Young Learners*. Cambridge UP, 2001.
6. Güçlü, B., Arslan, M., Üstünyer, İ. *Teaching Vocabulary İn Turkish Language For Foreigners At Beginner Level*. 2017.
7. Göçen, G. Türkçenin Yabancı Dil Olarak Öğretiminde Yöntem. *RumeliDE Dil ve Edebiyat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, (18), 23-48. 2020.
8. Pinter A. *Teaching Young Language Learners*. Oxford UP, 2017.
9. Larsen-Freeman D. *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. Oxford UP, 2011.
10. Wilkins, D. A. *Linguistics in Language Teaching*. London: Hodder and Stoughton Educational, 1972.

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER

ISSN 2782-4365
portal.issn.org/

2025